

The Rise of Social Media and its Impacts on Mainstream Media in Professional Journalism Observance in Zanzibar, Tanzania

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Abstract:

The emerge and uses of social media in the recent years, has rapidly developed to majority of journalists around Africa including Zanzibar, the energetic participation of the professional journalists in this technological innovation has widened space and impacted ethical principles of journalism as a professional and raised the doubt to the public on trusting the mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar. This article discussed the findings on how far the emerging of social media (Facebook) affect journalistic ethics observance notable 'truthfulness, objectivism, balance and fairness and accuracy' as a fundamental tool for the mainstream media journalism and how journalists used social media in their work. About 53.0% are on the views that social media affect principle of fairness, 46.34% journalists didn't observe ethical principle of objectivism in their reports, 66.3% of broadcasting journalists reports contained bias, 43.4% of the reports has less of facts check-up while 45.56% contain false information that was the huge impacts of social media on observed principle of truthfulness to majority of journalists in Zanzibar. There for 56.6% shows that broadcasting media in Zanzibar lost trust to the public, therefore from this factual perspectives special efforts needed to overcome continuation effects by emphasising on in-house training, more emphasis on news room ethics and codes with special

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social media guidelines will be useful to ovoid ethical dilemma on media professionalism in Zanzibar, Tanzania.

Keywords: Social media, Mainstream media, Facebook, journalistic ethics, Journalism,

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Introduction

Over the past years, technological developments have brought numerous changes in this world not only in political, economic and social but also the waves of changes blowing in the field of information and communication as well. Changes happened from printing press media, broadcasting media, in the recent years digital social media emerged. While the development has been hailed for facilitating previously marginalised people and groups to communicate effectively, there have been serious concerns on the implications of use of social media by journalists in their news reporting and questions have been raised on how this development relates to the ethical principles of journalism as a profession.

In journalism, the use of social media tools is the part of the new development in the communication revolution landscape not only in Zanzibar Island's media but to the world at large. Many media organization and journalists make use of them, but it raises questions of how uses and the impacts in view of media ethical principles to them when undertaking these new media platforms like Facebook. It should be effectively address the risk and impacts that media could face when using social media tools including truth, accuracy, balance, fairness and objectivism to ensure these ethical principles are highly considered in their report, this is because emerged of social media seem to cause breach of ethical principles of journalism which lead to media lose the credibility from the public. This study is going to observe the impact of social media on mainstream media journalism ethics as a fundamental element of the journalism especial in the context of Zanzibar media journalists. According to Ben-David, said "Unbalance news reporting actually from social media has harmful to mainstream media journalistic ethics according to study show that "herd mentality that render news coverage one-dimensional and one-sided, it has also resulted in the loss of credibility of the news reported (Ben-David, 2000). The Pew Research shows that "journalists widely use social media posts despite having doubts about their reliability...as journalist do less fact-checking"¹. Alia (2004) mentioned that there are three major areas of worldwide concern within the field of communication ethics as "truth, responsibility and free expression." (Alia, 2004: ix). According to the study done by (Pew, 2015), on German media professionals and journalists, it pointed out that 40 per cents of their thoughts are negative and they classify Facebook as negative, they don't trust the reliability of social media and also believe less in the importance of publishing first and then checking the facts

¹According to study done by USA TODAY/CNN/Gallup found that “confidence and accurate in media already went down and continue nowadays to slip found that 36 per cent of Americans believe news organizations get the facts straight, compared with 54 per cent in mid-1989”

A survey that was carried out to understand Turkish journalists “view ethics or whether they implement ethical codes among the 114 journalists show that journalists believe that journalists believe that journalists do not adhere to codes of professional practice and failure to accept ethical codes” (Koylu, 2006: 62-63). (The Pew Centre, 2005). Great thinker Michael Skoler argued as news conglomerates took over local news organizations and made changes people began losing trust in the media. Skoler wrote, “Surveys show a steep drop in public trust in journalism occurring during the past 25 years” (Skoler). The study conducted by Tendai Chari state that “While the ethical implications of these practices are not easy to pin down with precision, some sentiments from respondents suggest that fact-checking, accuracy and most importantly rigors, which are the hallmarks of traditional journalism ethics, might be under threat”². The survey also reported that “72% of the American public believes that the media favour one political party over the other instead of treating all parties equally” (The Pew Centre, 2005).

The revolution of media communication technology give the rise of social media by many journalists and media but actually according to researcher like Fisher, 2010; Sullivan, 2013a; 2013b, commented that “Social media have given rise to heated discussions over how journalists should use the media” (e.g. Fisher, 2010; Sullivan, 2013a; 2013b). Social-media-active journalists tend to deviate from traditional norms (Hedman & Djerf-Pierre, 2013), and audiences may take the deviation as a sign of unprofessionalism. Also the academician Borrowing Singer’s (2005) give out his expression on journalist used social media in their activities routine “challenges to professional norms as a non-partisan gatekeeper of information” (Borrowing Singer’s (2005) p.174)³. The distrust is huge problem in many countries including Zanzibar media as well, the study done in Turkey on how media observed the principle of truth in their report showed that, only one per cent of the respondents see the media as the most trusted institution in Turkey (Madra, 2006).

Also, Morozov criticized the social media that is not reliability he wrote, “This new media ecosystem is very much like the old game of ‘Telephone’ in which errors steadily

accumulate in the transmission process, and the final message has nothing in common with the original” (Morozov 11). Shumway and Berkman, 2001; Singer, 2001), in their study

²Tendai Chari, 2013. *New Communication Technologies and Journalism Ethics in Zimbabwe: Practices and Malpractices* University of Venda, South Africa

³J. Lee, (2015). *The Double-Edged Sword: The Effects of Journalists’ Social Media Activities on Audience Perceptions of Journalists and Their News Products*, the Weinstock Centre for Journalism, Lehigh University.

focus more on ethical dilemmas posed by new media technologies, its result show that the impact of new media technologies on traditional media, particularly in Africa remains anecdotal. However, some time some of the information reported through social media was correct, blogs and Twitter also may be responsible for spreading rumours” (Pew Research). While at the same time mainstream media journalists relying on social media it could be put in dilemma the issue of truth as a main principle of journalism. In the context of social media accuracy⁵ and in the study of Kaplan and Haenlein 2012), noted that in this world of social media revolution and mainstream media journalists relying on social media changes the traditional perspective on the journalist’s identity, with some theorists referring to it as the professional decline of journalism (Kaplan and Haenlein 2012). Actually, emerge and uses of social media in the recent years it brought the ethical dilemma to professionalism and raises the doubt to the public and trust the mainstream media journalists. Therefore, this study attempts to generate initial data on the impact of social media on journalism ethics, focusing on the experiences of Zanzibar’s journalists

About study area Zanzibar

Zanzibar is a semi-autonomous part of the United Republic of Tanzania (URT), located in the Indian Ocean East Africa. It is composed of the Zanzibar Archipelago in the Indian Ocean 35km off the coast of the Tanzania mainland Business city Dar es Salaam, and consists of two big Island Unguja and Pemba and more than 50 small islands surrounding. According to National Population Censuses held in 2012, indicated that Zanzibar has population of about 1.3 million. 58 per cent of population resides in rural while 42 in urban.

⁴ According to the study done by Cheney Thomas, (2013) about the impacts of social media to news broadcasting found from the respondent "I wouldn't say social media has improved journalism; it's made it different. In ways of speed and accuracy – speed has improved; accuracy has decreased. Width of information increased, but the depth has decreased. Journalism cannot live without social media, but social media can live without journalism." C. Thomas, (2013). The development of journalism in the face of social media: *A study on social media's impact on a journalist's role, method and relationship to the audience*, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden.

⁵ Patricia Sullivan, 2006, *Washington Post*, June 19, 2006,

DEVELOPMENT OF BROADCASTING MEDIA IN ZANZIBAR

The history of development of broadcasting media in Zanzibar started to be written around 1930's; by that time public media was used to communicate with the public act as a mouth of the rulers According to Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission (2016), At that time media monopolized by the government with one radio station (Sauti ya Unguja) and one Television station (tvz). After media liberalization by the end of 2015, the number of broadcasting media in Zanzibar and reached 23, including the four public broadcasting media, three community radios and 13 commercial broadcasting media stations has opened up and operate alongside the government media.

Statement of the problem

Social media platform is novel phenomenon and ideas to Zanzibar, it started to emerge and used by many Zanzibari in the recent years, this is due to the technological advancement and access of internet services in Zanzibar, it leads to many mainstream media journalists to use social media platforms like Facebook and others to facilitate their work. Although in the recent years, media broadcasting in Zanzibar seems to have been under increasing criticism for their lack of ethical principles of professionalism in their news reports due to the basically improper uses of social media platforms in their daily career routines. Due to the emerged of social media threatening the standards and ethical principles to media profession in Zanzibar and because of the unfamiliar of this field in Zanzibar which emerged and used around 1990's, and has no enough literature reviews and research particularly to the area of study.

Research Questions

This study focused on analysis the impacts brought by social media on mainstream media journalism professional regarding on the journalistic principles and ethics on news reporting professionalism.

Q1. How mainstream professional journalists in Zanzibar use social media in their daily routine activities?

Q2. How does the use of social media like Facebook overthrow the journalistic ethics and principles behaviours as fundamental tools of mainstream media news reporting?

Methodology

In this study, the survey and interview designed was used so as to analyse critically on how the mainstream media professional journalists in Zanzibar use social media in their daily routine activities and the also to understand deeply how far social media overthrow these professional ethical principles of journalism notably truth, accuracy, fairness, objectivism and balance as a foundermental tools for the mainstream media journalism professional practices in Zanzibar. In this study the researcher collected data from Zanzibar town and Urban-West Region of Unguja, because it was convenience to collect data since many journalists live at that area, accessibility of communication infrastructure such as internet availability, as well as being headquarters of almost all media existed in Zanzibar. Also this study included media professionals, journalists, and experience media experts, Officer from Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission who was responsible to supervise broadcasting media in Zanzibar and four officers from broadcasting media Organizations in Zanzibar Island. The number of people interviewed and fill the questionnaires were 100. Therefore, 95 were professional journalists and media experts; one respondent from Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission and Four officers from broadcasting media Organizations Zanzibar were interviewed. Basically, Probability with purposeful sampling technique was used. The criteria used to select these areas because many stations are locating in this area. One is the higher level number of the journalists living in this area and two is the accessibility to the area and internet services as well. The main instruments of data collection were Interviews and Constructive Questionnaires developed by the researcher regarding the journalistic ethical principles in Zanzibar.

Conceptual Framework

Journalistic Principles and Ethics

Journalism or media ethics is crucial in the field of professional journalism. Journalism as other professions has their own rules, principles and codes of ethics that guide the professionalism. There is a consensus among philosophers that ethics is synonymous with morality and both involve human action (conduct, behaviour) (Pratt, 1988). The word 'ethics' comes from the Greek word 'ethos' which means character, while the word 'morals' comes from the Latin word 'moralist' which means custom or manner (Okunna: 2003). In the simple meaning the ethics is a moral concept or rules or an a sanders governing the conduct of a person or the members of the particular professional groups or organization, every professional have their own codes of conduct and their own sets of ethical principles that direct the members of such society.

Moreover, observing media ethics will be based on values and principles of journalism professionals to determine which is right and which is wrong in the news and events reported by the media organization without ethics media is like a house without foundation, it will break. (Motamednejad, 2000). Media ethics consists of a series of covenants, behaviors, regulations, directives, and documents which the media editors or employees must adhere to in a society (Motamednejad, 2000). From multimedia to social media, the preponderance of digital technology in towards news work has the potential both to shift and reinforce journalists traditional norms and practices (Lasorsa, Lewis, and Holton 2012; Deuze and Marjoribanks 2009). Claudete, G. Artwick Lee, (2013). Therefore, among of journalism principles ethics that this study is dealing with is to see how far these ethical principles affected by the emerge and use of social media like a Facebook in their practices which include Truthfulness, Objectivism, Balance, Fairness and Accuracy as a key set elements of journalism.

Truthfulness

The journalists' role is to inform the public about what is happening in their environment and the world at large. Journalists are supposed to report on these truthfully and objectively. Truth is very important for journalism philosophical practise, although journalists cannot always guarantee the truth, but getting the actual facts is the key principle of journalism.

Actually relaying on social media like a Facebook as a sources of news, it can cost the mainstream media journalist every time when it comes the question of truth and accuracy of the information from them. Experts stress that the public are more likely to trust information that

comes from people they know. We use every social media outlet to find sources and track stories “According to Ward argues that journalism ethics too often falls back on simplistic appeals to general concepts such as “truth-seeking”, “freedom”, “serving the public” and “democracy”, terms which are highly contested (Ward, 2008:304). Weezel (2000) also quoted Meto and Iglesias (2000), said “ information quality begins with its truthfulness with the adaptation among the product that the media company offers and the reality that it tries to reflect”. In the matter of principle ethical of objectivism, Aveseh from Nigeria noted that “One of the editorial values that journalists and their organizations must ensure to adhere to is objectivity, if journalists do not verify stories that appear on social sites, just carry such stories because they want to be the first to break them, then they compromise objectivity” Aveseh, 2012)⁸.

⁸Asough, A. (2012), Social Media and Ethics - *The Impact of Social Media on Journalism Ethics*, Focus: The Ethical Challenges of Journalists Using Social Media Websites in Their Reporting. Abuja, Nigeria.

Balance and Fairness

Balance and fairness are the basic catchwords of journalism ethics, among the basic roles of mainstream media journalists is to inform the public about the political, canonical and social issues surround their environment, by implementing this task; the news must be balanced in the sense of attempting to present and reporting all sides of the news in terms of confidentiality and credibility on linking of news sources and information without any dilemma. Fairness means that a professional journalist should be strive for accuracy and truth in their reporting and should treat equally all those who were interviewed and report on with scrupulous fairness, guided by professionalism not to viewpoint a story so as readers can draw the reporter’s desired conclusion. Some (Sutter, 2001) boldly claim that a bias media is a failure of the news market. Fico & Cote broke down bias into two components: Fairness and balance. Fairness is defined as the presence of quoted or paraphrased assertions by sources supporting both. Balance is about how people are treated by the journalist reports equally.⁹

Objectivism

Objectivity in the field of journalism simply it means the journalists to make sure to observe and seeking out of truth, impartiality and fairness as a matter of searching for accurately and

facts evidence in the reporting. Objectivism involves fairness and impartiality, which means correct reflection of the opinions of rival parties during a debate. Publishing the opinion of the opposing parties from a wrong source of news or from a single source, Journalistic objectivity has two components first is 'depersonalization' which means that journalists should not overtly express their own views, evaluations, or beliefs, and the second is 'balance' which involves presenting the views of representatives of both sides of a controversy without favouring one side. (Entman, 1989, p.30; Nelkin 1987, p 91). According to MaNair (1998), cited by Samwilu Mwaffisi, (2011), defined three characteristics of objectivity in journalism field including “the separation of facts and opinion, a balance account of a debate and the validation of journalistic statements by references to authoritative others”.

⁹“Reporting issues fairly requires not only factual accuracy, but also lack of favouritism toward any organization, political group, ideology, or other agenda” (Fico & Cote, 1999, p. 127). will be harmful, one-sided reporting might have destructive effects and will be dangerous from a legal point of view (Harris, 2002, p. 36).

Accuracy

When a quote presented either literal or verbal should be in reality ways but several reporters used social media platform like a Facebook as their sources of news it seems they faced the issue of publishing inaccurate reporting and false news since journalism need facts checking and verifying for accuracy. “The usual practice is to verify quotes with the sources and to double check all the fact by requiring two independent sources confirm them” Joseph, S. and Robart, R. (2000). Therefore, accuracy include double-check facts, figures, names, dates and spellings and the responsible person journalist should watch the typographic errors in the news, Study shows that fewer reporters on fewer beats, fewer news angles presented and fewer facts checked, and less inspired storytelling (Pew, 2012). According to the Committee of Concerned Journalists asserts, “Accuracy is the foundation upon which everything else will be built context, interpretation, comment, criticism, analysis and debates, so reliable news sources are so essential”. Bregtje, H. & Michael, P.(2012).

ZANZIBAR BROADCASTING COMMISSION (ZBC)

Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission established by the Zanzibar Broadcasting Act No.7, 1997. The duties and responsibilities of this Commission are including the issuance of broadcasting

licences, regulation and supervision of broadcasting activities, protection of broadcasting policy, security, culture and tradition of Zanzibar, inspection of institutions offering broadcasting services in Zanzibar Island, and even giving direction to the broadcasting business in whatever manner deems necessary¹⁰.

Table 1. Sample Composition by Category and Respondent

Type	Target	Reached	Unreached	Analysed
Journalists	95	83	12	83
Officers from Media	4	4	0	4
Officer from ZBC	1	1	0	1
TOTAL	100	88	12	88

Source: Computed from Collected data 2017

¹⁰According to Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission Act, 2007

¹¹Wimmer, R. D. & Dominick, J. R. (2011). *Mass media research: an introduction*. (9th edition) California: Wadsworth, Cengage Learning

Respondents' Profile

A total of 83 respondents filled questionnaires whereby 47 were female which is 56.6% of the respondents, while 36 were male which is about 43.4% of the respondents, Moreover, in this study the participants were categorized in terms of age, about 61.4 respondents were under the age between 20-30 years old, 24.1% aged between 30-40 years old, whereby 8.4% aged above 40 years while only 6% of the respondents were under the age of 20. Overall total age between male and female under 20 years of age was 6.0%, between 20 and 30 years of age total 61.40%, the age between 30 and 40 combine 24.10% total while the total per cent above 40 years between male and female is 8.40% as depict in the Figure 2 below

Figure 2: Respondents' Profile 'Gender and Age'

Source: Computed from Collected Field Data 2017

The figure 3 below depicts the numbers of social media which many journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar preferred to use in their daily routine, 50 respondents about 61.0% of the journalists preferred to use Facebook in their daily activities in broadcasting media in Zanzibar, followed by WhatsApp whereby 26 respondent equal to 31.7% of the journalists used it, while 5 respondent equal to 6.1% used Instagram, whereas only 1 respondent comprised of 1.2% used Twitter in is daily activities.

Figure 3. Show the Category of Social Media Respondents preferred to use in their daily activities

Source: Computed from Collected Field Data 2017

Basically, one of the intentions of this study was to examine the real situation on how a journalist uses social media in their daily routine. The result shows that 44 respondents about 53.0% used social media to read the local, national and global news, about 41.0% used for facilitating news gathering, reporting and distribution of information while remaining 6.0% of the respondents they just used social media platforms to keep in touch with friends and to be entertained. See Table 2. Below

Table 2: Show the result on how journalist used social media daily life

Respondent	Frequency	Valid Per cent
To read local, national and global news	44	53.0%
To keep in touch with friends and be entertained	5	6.0%
For facilitating news gathering, reporting and distributions	34	41.0%

Findings result of social media effect on ethical principles of Balance and Fairness.

The researcher wanted to understand on how far social media affects mainstream media ethical principles of balance and fairness since journalists in Zanzibar started to use social media platforms as a source of their news coverage. To assess the impacts of using social media in this aspect of ethics, after shaping the questions which were asked to journalists that, "lack of balance is the major ethical dilemma of mainstream media journalism in Zanzibar which is persistently practiced after emerging uses of social media (Facebook). Do you agree?" According to this question the respondents were divided into groups from the journalists and media officers, from the journalists the highest value 62.7% Agree that lack of balance is the major ethical dilemma in the mainstream media journalism, 20.5% Strongly Agree while 9.6% Disagree where by 6 journalists about 7.2% strongly disagree with that statement. Basically, these results depict the certainty from the journalists themselves to agree that lack of balance is the major ethical dilemma of mainstream media journalism in Zanzibar, as demonstrated in the Figure 4 below.

Source: computed from collected data 201

On the other hand one respondent from media officers said that according to the issue of balance of news means that since some of the journalists have a background knowledge about computers and uses of social media platforms but others did not grow up with internet to social media prior to just started to use social media at working areas and even this technology was very new never used before by the media in Zanzibar and started to be used by many mainstream media organization in Zanzibar in recent years. In the matter of balance of news and good uses of social media question was asked to media organizations officers if they think that “social media platform like Facebook are used properly by the mainstream broadcasting journalists in Zanzibar according to ethical principles of professionalism?”. The results from the interviewee one of them show satisfaction but others did not satisfy on how mainstream media worked in Zanzibar, one of the interviewee claimed that;

“I am not satisfied,because there are some media tries to follow the ethics principles of the journalism or press but there are other broadcasting media institutions which do not follow the ethics principles of the press here in Zanzibar. For Example, government broadcasting media tend to provide their information on one side, which is the government information only. Also many of the Zanzibar journalists do not balance their news reporting... basically caused by some of their news sources failing to cooperate with the media in Zanzibar”.

Also, another officer from Zanzibar Broadcasting Commission (ZBC) said;

“On the other hand, is used by the journalists to provide and circulate information unsubstantiated and incorrect and often information that is unbalanced and typically laying on one side and the journalists used such unbalanced information in their news reporting which is going against the ethical principles of the journalism professionalism”. Commented officer from ZBC

Balance of news in any way is among crucial elements in professional journalism ethics and the journalists who used social media should be more considerate to this element in their working activities, but to large extent it seemed to be an issue for journalists who depend on social media platforms as sources of their news in Zanzibar. Therefore, a question was asked to the respondents “Do you think that news from Facebook is credible and present both side of the responsible sources that can be used by mainstream media journalist in Zanzibar?” The results of this question depicts that 62.7% of the respondents say No, while 26.5% of respondent said Yes, while 10.8% they Don’t know, according to this result it means that majority of the respondents said No that news from social media platforms like Facebook was not credible and did not present both side of the responsible sources that can be used by mainstream media journalist in Zanzibar, the Table 3 below portray the result.

Table 3: Indicate the views of journalists on balance of news sources from social media.

Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Yes	22	26.5%
No	52	62.7%
Don't know	9	10.8%
Total	83	100.0%

Source: computed from collected data 2017

Effects of Social Media on Ethical Principle of Fairness

In the principles of news gathering and broadcasting, the journalists should treat the respondents who are named or associated to the news equally and fairly, so by using social media as a sources of news how the impact that social media brought to journalism professionals. To find out, the question was asked to respondents that “According to your experience on using social media as your sources of information do you think the news from

social media like Facebook treating the sources equally?” The result pointed out that 78.31% which was the highest result marked No, which means that the news from social media was not treating the sources of news fairly, 16.87% said Yes and last 4.82% of the respondents answered that the Don’t know. See Figure 5 below.

Source:

computed from collected data 2017

In this ethical principle of fairness the important element including the credibility and enough sources of news, in this context the survey found that about 62 respondents that make 74.7% which was very high result Agree that news from social media was not credible and do not have enough sources, 18 respondents equal to 13.3% showed Strongly agree, whereby 6 respondents disagree with statement and 4 respondents who make 4.8% Strongly disagree with the statement that news from social media is not credible and lack of enough sources. But generally according to these results, the news from social media was not credible and lack of balance sources. Table 4 below shows the results.

Table 4: Shows the respondent results news from social media was not credible and enough sources

Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Strongly agree	11	13.3%
Agree	62	74.7%
Disagree	6	7.2%
Strongly Disagree	4	4.8%
TOTAL	83	100.0%

Source: Computed from Collected Data on Field 2017

In addition on this ethical principle of fairness, the researcher wanted to know the views of journalists themselves how do they think for the journalists' relying on social media affect the principle of fairness. The result illustrates that 53.0% respondents said Yes means for journalist relying on social media affected journalistic ethical principle of fairness, while 26.5% of the respondents said No, comparing to 20.5% who said they Don't know for the journalists uses social media platform affected the journalism ethical principle of fairness. Some of the respondents who said No provided common reason, one of them said;

"Some people and others journalists used social media like Facebook and others for their personal or political interest for the personal benefit rather than public or promoting development issues, so if the professional elite journalists relying on story based on social media without efforts to verify them it can cause problems"

Therefore, under this perspective it is clear that for the journalists who relying on social media as their sources of news to broadcast typically affected the ethical principles of fairness of professional journalism in Zanzibar Island as figure 6 demonstrates below.

Source: Computed from Collected Data on Field 2017

Beside the result that has been shown above, on Table 5 below also the results shoes about 57.8% of respondents emphasis that the use of social media like Facebook in mainstream media journalism did not present all side of the news sources fairly in their reports, whereby, 24.1% they think that the mainstream media journalist by using news from social media like Facebook present all sides of the news sources fairly in their reports, on other side 15 respondents equal to 18.1% said they don't know. These results provide the clear picture on

how using social media platforms like Facebook for journalist could affect the journalists to handle the ethical principles of fairness.

Table 5: Respondents' opinion on journalism if social media present all sides of the news sources fairly in their report

Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Yes	20	24.1%
No	48	57.8%
Don't know	15	18.1%
TOTAL	83	100.0%

Source: Computed from Collected Data on Field 2017

Effect of social media on the aspect of Objectivism

The researcher wanted to prove on how the uses of social media platform (Facebook) by the journalist brought the significance effects to the professional ethic of Objectivism to the mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar Island. Objectivism implies the aspects of fairness including neutrality and impartiality. The result indicate that 46.35% of the respondents said to a little extent that mainstream media observe the principle of objectivism in their news broadcasting reports, 30.49% said there are very few mainstream media journalists who observed principles of objectivism in their news broadcasting reports, about 12.20% said very much few mainstream media journalists who observed the ethical principle of objectivism in their news reports, whereby 10.980% who agree that the mainstream media journalists obviously possible they observed ethical principle of objectivism in their report even if they relying on social media platforms. See The Figure 7.

Source: Computed from Collected Data on Field 2017

So far the Figure 8 illustrates the impact of social media basically to the aspect of neutrality in their news reporting, so the question asked to the respondents that “to what extent does mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar Broadcasting news organizations regarding neutrality (impartiality) in news coverage?” The results was that 45 respondents, about 54.2% said the extent of the broadcasting news organizations regarding the aspect of neutrality were little in news coverage, in relation to 25 respondents 30.1% who said broadcasting organizations in Zanzibar regarding very little aspect of neutrality in their news coverage from social media, whereby 10 respondents about 12.0% said media organizations regarding very much little the principle of objectivism in the aspect of neutrality in their news coverage while 10 respondents who comprise 3.6% only of the total respondents they said it possible for the mainstream media organization regarding neutrality in their news coverage, this is due to the fact that in figure 7 below. Represent the fact for the majority of the professional media organizations journalists after using social media platforms like Facebook as their sources of gathering information disregard the principles ethic of objectivism according to the aspects of neutrality in their coverage.

Source: Computed from Collected Data on Field 2017

Moreover, the study finds that broadcasting journalists in news media in Zanzibar have bias in news coverage and reporting. From the answers provided by the respondents from the question that asked “On your experiences do you agree that broadcasting journalists in Zanzibar news media have bias in news coverage and reporting since the mainstream media journalists used social media platform especially Facebook?” From this question, 66.3% the highest number of respondents agree that broadcasting journalists in Zanzibar news media have bias in news coverage and reporting since the mainstream media journalists used social

media platform especially Facebook, while 24.1% said No bias in news coverage and reporting but only 9.6% of the respondents who Don't know if the journalists in news media in Zanzibar have bias in news coverage and reporting.

Table 6: Respondents' result on journalists' bias in news coverage and reporting from social media platform

Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Yes	55	66.3%
No	20	24.1%
Don't Know	8	9.6%
TOTAL	83	100.0%

Source: Collected Data from Field 2017

As can be noted in (Figure 6, Figure 8 and Table 6) above, therefore, I can assert that the researcher's hypothesis was supported by the respondents and in the opinion of the journalists and editors and broadcasting media officers that mainstream media journalists do not observed the ethical principle of Objectivism in their reports since they started to use and relying on social media platform in their daily routine, this study shows clear picture on how social media.

Effects of social media on mainstream media ethic of Accuracy

The researcher also examines on how the practice of journalism using social media platforms like Facebook as a sources of news may effect a broadcasting media journalisms ability to comply with the ethical standards principle of accuracy in Zanzibar. The results from the respondents shows that, about 48.2% respondents said No totally they believed that social media is not good sources of the news should journalist relaying on them as one of the respondent claimed that;

"There are multiple generation of journalists working in broadcasting media in Zanzibar nowadays, not all of them are going to observe ethical principles like accuracy they just broadcast

the news even if is not accurately, well investigating and this is the big mistake, as journalists we are doing every day in our activities we consider social media stories are perfect that it is”

Another respondent who is a senior reporter claimed that majority of the journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar who relying on social media platforms like Facebook as their sources of news do not consider the accuracy of the news from this technological age.

“Nowadays every one is a journalist, they put out their staffs and post whatever they want to post on internet like Facebook even the false reports for them no any consequences, but the trap challenge when many journalists in Zanzibar fall into is using this information as if it has been verified information that pick up from social media like Facebook and so on.....Actually, journalists in Zanzibar should be stand on their ethical principles especially accuracy as we have been trained” One of the journalist claimed.

Nevertheless, all journalists need to be vigilant about accuracy of their work every time, but broadcasting journalists who used social media as the sources of news may have a special obligation to be particularly careful with the information from there. Also, another journalist who responded to this question in his comments noted that;

“every journalists working harder to become more current and to be the first to break the news which gathered from social media platforms like Facebook but the problem become in the issue of verifying the credibility and accuracy of the news from social media this is problem that many journalists we faced right now..”

Although some of the journalists who believed that news from social media like Facebook is the good sources of news where the journalist should rely on them to find a story idea of follow up the trend of the stories, but one among of the respondent who said No;

“I do believe that for the professional journalists should not rely on social media as a sources of news like Facebook, as you know on social media anyone can say anything, some lie, have agendas to push forwards and have individual biases all of these aspects affecting accuracy and credibility of information they used to broadcast while the individual is not accountable for what they write, problems come to us as a journalist” One of the Journalist commented.

On other side, the results show that only 26.5% respondents said Yes they think that social media is the good sources of news should journalist rely on them, comparing to 25.3% who do not know if the social media is good sources of news or not for the journalists relaying on. Social media tried to fed the journalists faster than before, the problem is how to verify the accuracy of the news from internet since when people post the information in the social media within few hours or minute information removed, accuracy its remain vital ethic of professional journalism to be well observe when using social media platforms. Figure 9 below show the result of this question.

Source: Computed from Collected Data from Field 2017

In addition, the broadcasting media officers who were interviewee in this study said that majority of journalists used social media in a bad way it means basically is not a good sources of news because majority they did not follow the ethical principle of accuracy in their news gathering. One interviewee claimed that;

“Social networking is not used properly by the journalists in Zanzibar, journalists use the story from social media as it is and just used them in their broadcasting media channels without ascertaining the truth and accuracy of the relevant information from the sources of the news and the absence of laws that guidelines the proper use of social networks also it contributes the bad uses of social media network by the majority of journalists in Zanzibar”. **Claimed one interviewee**

Accuracy is most important element of consideration and is the central reason for what of any journalists should bear in mind when he or she is working for media for reputation of their

work and media organization as well. The respondents' results from this question the finding depict that 27.7% of the respondents said that false information was the most dominant impacts of social media (Facebook) on the matter of consideration of element of accuracy on mainstream media news stories, whereby 26.5% considered copy and paste was the most dominant impacts of social media on mainstream media news stories, than 24.1% said spreading rumors was the most dominant impacts of social media Facebook on the mainstream media news stories while only 21.7% they said less fact check was the most dominant social media impacts on broadcasting news stories. According to the findings it was proved that the social media was huge impacts on mainstream media journalism. As shown in the Figure 10 below.

Source: Computed from Collected Data from Field 2017

In order to get the clear picture on how the social media impacted mainstream media ethics principle of accuracy the question asked to respondent just to rate the level of accuracy, "In your opinion, how would you rate the accuracy of the mainstream media news broadcasting organizations on Facebook in Zanzibar?". From the study results substantiate that 44.6% said the accuracy of mainstream media broadcasting in Zanzibar was fair it means to some extent journalists tried to consider the element of accuracy in their news story even if they gathered from social media platforms like Facebook, whereby 27.7% they said the level of accuracy was poor, while only 4.8% of the journalists believed that accuracy was very poor in mainstream media organizations, the remaining journalists 22.9% of the total of the respondents rated the level of accuracy in broadcasting media organizations in Zanzibar was good. Their base in these findings provides a clear picture that the level of accuracy to mainstream media journalists

organizations in Zanzibar since they started to use social media the level of accuracy in their news stories was fair but on the other side even if it was not in a large amount the social media contributed to some extent to breach the ethical principle of accuracy to mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar. As figure 11 revealed the results.

Source: Computed from Collected Data from Field 2017

Effects of social media on fundamental ethical principle of truthfulness

The aspect of Truthfulness whereby the researcher wanted to know how this ethical principle of professional journalism affected when the broadcasting media journalists in Zanzibar started to use social media platforms like Facebook.

Table 7. Shows the respondent's problems encountered by using social media regarding journalism ethics principle of telling truth story

Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Less fact	36	43.4%
Few credible sources	26	31.3%
Grammar and Spelling error	7	8.4%
False information	14	16.9%
TOTAL	83	100.0%

Source: Computed from Collected Data from Field 2017

For the journalists, telling the truth is a fundamental ethical principle of professionalism whereby any journalist has to emphasize to consider in their daily activities. This study required to find out how social media affect the journalistic ethical principle of truthfulness when the journalists used social media in their daily routine, in order to achieve the target objective the

researcher asked the respondents that “What problems have you encountered by using social media regarding journalism ethics principle of telling truth story?”, the results in the table 7 above pointed out those 36 respondents equal to 43.4% faced the problem of less of facts story when they used social media platform, in relation to 26 respondents about 31.3% said that faced the story from social media was few credible sources, while 14 respondents which comprised 6.9% said they faced false information when they used social media gathering stories, the remaining 7 respondents only 8% of the total journalists said they faced the problem of grammar and spelling error when they used social media news. But it’s important to note here that for a journalist to verifying (fact check) information especially from social media platforms is to get justification the accuracy of the information unfortunately mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar seemed to perform poorly when it comes the matter of observing accuracy in the news report

Also, during interview one question that was asked to the broadcasting and ZBC Officers if they think that social media platforms like Facebook was used properly by the journalists in Zanzibar, one of the broadcasting media officers comment in relation to the ethical principle of truthfulness and said that;

“Actually apart from the truth that social media technology was very new to our media organization and many journalists didn’t know how to use basically in the issue of telling the truth on stories, to large extent it believed that many information from social media opinionated rather than facts and truth, than that the sources from which individuals post and the professional journalists just received the particular information are not as reliable as sources from which journalists supposed to get information” Commented one of the interviewed officer.

Figure 12: Depict the respondents' opinion of common impacts of social media towards the professional ethic principle of truth.

Source: Collected Data from Field 2017

Also, in this aspect of truthfulness the data from this study deeply found that false information was the common impact when the journalists used social media (Facebook) towards their professional ethic of truth about 45.56% of respondents was experienced this impact, while 28.89% of respondents said rumour is the common impacts of social media to journalists professional ethics of truth, than 12.22% said that favour one side the common impact of social media where journalists experienced, while only 5.56% of the total survey respondents believed that common impacts when journalists used social media like Facebook towards professional principle of truth was spread speculations and 7.78% were missing. Obviously, the result gives the picture that social media used by the journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar effect the journalism professional ethic principle of truthfulness where by journalists they didn't consider the truth effectively in their news coverage and reporting. Figure 12 above provides clear image of impacts that already happen towards professional ethic of truthfulness since the journalists in Zanzibar started to use social media (Facebook)

Another important thing in this part is the aspect of reliability of the news from social media where by the mainstream media relying on them, the researcher asked the opinion of the journalists that "Is news from social media reliable and worthy of being broadcasting on mainstream media?" this is because the truthfulness of the news obviously going simultaneously with the reliability and worthy of the news to be broadcasting, Study revealed that 47.0% they said impossible that news from social media wasn't credible and worthy to be broadcasting, while 45.8% respondent said possible to be broadcasting news from social media was credible and worthy, but 3.6% respondent said very possible to broadcasting news from social media and the rest 3.6% of the journalists said very impossible to broadcasting the news from social media because was not credible and worthy as shown on table 8.

Table 8. Expressed the respondents' opinion on the reliability and worthy of news from social media

Respondent	Frequency	Valid Percentage
Very Possible	3	3.6%
Possible	38	45.8%
Impossible	39	47.0%
Very Impossible	3	3.6%

TOTAL	83	100%
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Source: Collected Data from Field 2017

Discussion

How Social Media Overthrow the Journalistic Ethical Behaviours in News Reporting in Zanzibar?

According to the findings shows that journalists used social media in two ways, social media become the eyes and ears of the mainstream media journalists it facilitated some of the journalists to used them for news reading, gathered and distribution of local, national and international news as a vital responsibility of the professional journalist where the aim is to inform the public all events that happened in the society and world in general for the benefit for their life as shown in the Table 2. This study on other side revealed that the uses of social media platforms like Facebook in the news media organizations was not actually satisfied, this is because many journalists and media broadcasting officers as well supported this notion, according to the survey results show that 50.6% of the journalists who filled questionnaire they didn't satisfied on how mainstream media journalists used Facebook according to their professional ethics of the journalisms compare to 32.5% who said the journalists used social media properly (see figure 13). Basically the impacts of social media were divided in to four parts according to the ethical principles of journalism that the researcher examined on them on how the social media effects the principles of Truthfulness, accuracy, balance and fairness as well as principle of objectivism.

Discussion on the elements of Truthfulness and Accuracy

Truth is the most highly regarded as a fundamental journalistic ethical valuable principle of professionalism, whereby public all the time expect nothing from the broadcasting media journalists then telling information truthfully. Among the aspect of truth is that the journalists reporting must be accurate it means that the fact should be verifying if there is any doubt, in this study revealed that majority of the news from social media where professional journalists relying on them was not accurate and less fact check-up from credible recognized sources but in this study (see Figure 13) these findings indicate that journalists' social media that almost 49.4% believed that false information was the huge impact that happen to the journalists in

Zanzibar, nowadays since after relying on social media as their sources of news while 31.3% of the respondent they said journalists used rumours story from social media so capacity of verifying the facts was decrease they satisfied to relying on them that is why social media become a driving sources by feeding the majority of news events and conversations from social media platforms such as Facebook and then broadcasting media professional used to pick up the information posted and packaged them and ready for mass media audiences, actually, this is the new style of copy and paste which are unacceptable in the world of journalism as a professional, for a journalists news must be reported truthfully.

This survey depicts that less of fact check is part of the effect that journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar practiced after engaging on used social media platforms like Facebook, many journalists exposed that they did less facts check-up of their story based on social media platforms about 43.4 faced this problem of less fact check-up story while 31.3% said encountered the story on Facebook has few credible sources but they used as it is, even though it is going against the professional ethics of the journalism. They did not verify the facts of their story well. The professional journalist strongly tends to view themselves as defenders of the credible public information based on their methods of collecting and verifying the facts from the sources of the information. In the aspect of telling the truth the news report should be fair and balance, this was the essential element of truthfulness where the study examined the result as shown in (Table 5) depict the clear picture that 66.3% of respondent said that broadcasting news media journalists has a bias in their news coverage and reporting, from this result means that since mainstream media journalists in Zanzibar started to use social media platform like Facebook to large extent were affect their ethic principles of truthfulness and accuracy as a professional. The important things to journalists here is recognize those views that enhance the understanding of an issues that have been associated with the information including the credible sources and present them fairly according to the news context, certify the news content and must to avoid any personal comments as well.

Basically, accuracy can be achieved when the relevant facts in the news reporting are well putting in the proper context, where there is a reason to doubt the accuracy of the report and it is practicable to verify the accuracy that report should be verified by the journalists and media organizations. In this survey shows that 27.7% of the story from social media platforms where journalists in Zanzibar used contain false information whereby 26.5% of respondents

said the journalists just used the way of copy and paste the news from social media as it is and then 21.7% said journalists has less facts check to ensure the accuracy and credibility of the information from social media platforms like Facebook (see figure 9), there for it is very likely social media capability to be such medium of effect the accuracy of mainstream media journalism ethics, since the mainstream media journalists based on social media, as well as their credibility. Every day and every time public rightly expects credible and accuracy news from professional journalists, and has a right to be served by the honest professional journalists from mainstream news media organization to feed them with an accurate report. but in this survey portray that many journalists they used social media as their primary sources is like a copy and paste news, false information, and les fact check-up as well as relaying on single sources (see table 5.), this is the worst things that many journalists did that affect their ethical principle of accuracy.

How social media effect ethical principle of Objectivism

The traditional role of journalists as out lined within normative theories is to provide objective and accurate reporting without distorting or intervening in the news (McQuail, 2010). According to the code of conduct journalists have duties to maintain the highest professional and ethical principles standards of journalism. Objectivity is an indispensable journalistic ideal, however, that all people are subjective, partial and biased in nature as a human being, but professional journalists ethically need to be observe the element of Objectivism (neutrality) in their reporting because it can help the journalists and media to be credible to public, unfortunately in this survey shows that (see Table 8), 54.2% of respondents agree that a little extent the journalists regards the aspect of neutrality while 30.1% also said very little journalists regards aspect of neutrality in their reports, here it means that journalists did not put more consideration on ethical of objectivism, results give out the big picture that broadcasting media journalists in Zanzibar used to broadcast news with bias instead reporting issues in a partially (neutrality) manner.

Figure 13: Shows the respondents time spend on social media (Facebook) a week

Source: Collected Data from Field 2017

Objectivity is highly important aspect on professional journalism where by public and journalists themselves should be more prized professionally, while in other hand the results still illustrated that journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar regarded the principle of objectivism in a little extent as if is not important to be consider in their daily activities as shown in the (figure 5) that 46.3% said journalists in Zanzibar regarded principle of objectivism in a little extent while 30.5% said journalists regarded principle of objectivism very little, so that this is the dilemma of professionalism ethic that caused by the journalist in Zanzibar to engage on using social media. The reality is that, the good professional journalists always do not evolve in the story nor do they allow their own convictions to influence a story or to express preference to favour one side of the story and even to reflects their attitudes about the specific group of people and events involved, so the only important way to journalists to make sure that reporting the facts effectively as it is. This objectivity is very essential ethic principle which linked to truth whereby practically the truth has capable of being reported objectively in a correct way according to the context of the news.

Social media effects on principles of Balance and Fairness

Balance and fairness are important ethical element that all journalists should understand and this is among the basic principles of journalism, this because unbalance and fair reporting can cause harm towards the public and victimized as well. In this world of social media innovation many journalists seemed to be far from preventing these ethical principles effectively and falling down to themselves on relying on social media without consideration of professional

ethics principles. According to these findings indicate that journalists' social media uses 62.7% of respondent agree that lack of balance in the news story was the major ethical dilemma of mainstream media journalism broadcasting in Zanzibar which was persistently practiced after emerged used of social media platforms like Facebook journalists in broadcasting media in Zanzibar, stressing on that 20.5% respondent strong agree on this concept, here it means that means that majority of journalists agree that used of social media affected them on practiced ethical principle of balance in their news reports as professional journalist. When the journalists the more unbalance and unfair they are, it can lead them to create greater harm to the public.

Reporting fairness, however, it doesn't matter for the journalists gives all side of an issues the same amount of coverage but it depends to the important and relevant information facts of the news sources. However, this study discovered that majority of broadcasting media journalists in Zanzibar didn't practices ethical principle of fairness, because they were relaying on social media, this study shows that 53.0% of journalists agree that social media affected the professional principle of fairness (see Figure 6) also because majority of journalists used Facebook in their daily routine 57.8% said mainstream media didn't present all sides parts of the news sources equally (see Table 4), here it means that journalists in mainstream media in Zanzibar have bias and unfair in their reporting which are the huge effects to their professional ethics of being balance and fair in their news reporting to their public audience. Professionally, journalists should be fair in their reporting aiming to give all sides of an issue the right time to heard or replay, should present the facts without bias, under emphasis. Unaccepted journalistic behaviours news obtained dishonest sources or unfair means should not broadcast on media. Nowadays, the uses of social media platforms in Zanzibar broadcasting media is unavoidable particularly to the journalists, the important question that needed to be in mind of them is on how they use social media by consideration of ethical principles of the professionalism. All the time public need truth and accurate information to be informed, truth and accurate news reporting always build a good relationship in terms of trust between the broadcasting journalist and media with audiences. Social network has become mainstream activities, fundamentally changing the nature of the news, mainstream media organizations as they marry the culture of the social media platforms norms that is why social media guidelines must be written and follows by the mainstream media journalists as a professional.

Conclusion and recommendations

The intention of this study was to examine how far the rise of social media platforms like Facebook impacts the mainstream media in professional journalism observance of ethical principles of journalism included truthfulness, accuracy, objectivism as well as balance and fairness as fundamental elements of broadcasting journalism especially in Zanzibar. The good ways to overcome all ethical dilemma to professional journalists uses of Media self-regulation body is very important for the accountability and flourish of broadcasting landscape not only in Zanzibar itself but also around the Africa and world in general, Clear writing codes and regulations covering media ethics and its consequences should be written and well implemented by the media organizations, ZBC and broadcasting media organizations should promote capacity building of the journalists and media practitioners, Establishment of non-state professional monitoring board it will help to make monitoring and make follow up the trend of the media ethics uses and make suggestion for better uses, Media literacy education is very important for the society and journalists themselves for better uses of social media, Conducting In-house training and even Zanzibar should introduce its own national communication policy, there for by doing that it will help the mainstream media journalist to observe ethical principles and good uses of social media towards the national development in general.

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